

Estimation of the strain field from full-field displacement noisy data : filtering through Diffuse Approximation and application to interlock graphite/epoxy composite

P. Feissel, J. Schneider and Z. Aboura

Laboratoire Roberval de Mécanique, UTC,
BP 20529 rue Personne de Roberval 60205 COMPIEGNE
pierre.feissel@utc.fr

Abstract — This study presents a tool for numerical differentiation of perturbed displacement fields in order to obtain the strain field. The proposed approach lies on the Diffuse Approximation [1] and allows a filtering of the noise while aiming at controlling the loss of mechanical information within the strain field. The method is applied to the case of a tensile test on a satin composite where the displacement are yielded by CORRELIQ4 [2], a numerical image correlation tool. The choice of optimal parameters in the coupling of the two tools (correlation and filtering) is also adressed and a first criterium is proposed.

Keywords — full field measurements, numerical differentiation, identification, filtering.

1 Introduction

The recent development of digitized full-field displacement measurements opens new ways of characterizing materials in solid mechanics [1]. When dealing with composites with large heterogeneities, the full-field technique allows a much richer description of the behaviour during the test than when using standard strain gauges. However, for most of the users of these techniques the strain fields rather than the displacement fields provide a real insight into the physics of the material at different scales. Therefore, except for the techniques which provide directly the displacement derivatives, it is necessary to differentiate the data. When the gradients of the displacement fields are relatively low, for example when the materials still behave elastically, the small measurement errors may induce large errors on the computed derivative [2]. So the key work is to develop a stable algorithm, in which it is possible to quantify explicitly the effects induced by noise differentiation.

A large number of algorithms can be found in the literature, [3]. One widely used way of performing this filtering consists in interpolating or approximating the data using smooth basis functions. The differentiation of the data is turned into the differentiation of the basis functions. For a given basis of functions, the regularization parameter is tied to the number of functions used in the basis. A good compromise between the faithfulness of the reconstruction (obtained with a large number of basis functions) and the efficiency of the low pass filtering (obtained with a small number of basis functions) has to be found.

However, a good choice of the basis functions is essential [4]. Previous studies [5] showed that a global polynomial basis leads to parasitic oscillations in the reconstruction when the degree

of the polynomials is too large. Indeed, because of the global aspect of this type of bases, local artifacts in the data affect the whole reconstruction. Accordingly, it seems that basis functions that have limited interactions between each other would be more appropriate.

In [5], two filtering approaches were compared, one based on a global least-square and a Finite Element basis, the other one based on local least squares and polynomial basis, based on the Diffuse Approximation [1]. The two approaches yield similar results in terms of approximation error and filtering ability and can be tuned thanks to a length parameter ; nonetheless, the approach based on the Diffuse Approximation is not suffering from the dependency of the reconstructed strain field to the meshing (since there is no meshing) and offers a suited theoretical background for the controlling of the error. This approach is therefore adopted here, even though its computing time was larger.

The Diffuse Approximation filtering technique is applied here to experimental data in order to address its efficiency. The chosen test is a $\pm 45^\circ$ traction test on an interlock composite beam. The full-field measurements are performed by digital image correlation (DIC), through the CORRELIQ4 software [2]. The first question that is addressed in the paper is to discuss how to tune the parameters of both the correlation software and the filtering tool in order to improve the filtering while keeping a good local mechanical information. A pragmatic criterium based on virtual strain gauges is then proposed in order to yield a maximum value of the filtering parameter to limit the mechanical information loss. Finally, based on the ideas proposed in [3], we try to localize the development of local non-linearities during the test.

2 Reconstruction of the strain field from the displacement field

2.1 Framework and notations

The proposed approach aims at reconstructing the strain field from displacement data, whatever the technique could be to get the latter (DIC or grid method, for example). The measurement zone is denoted Ω and the input data are the displacements on a regular grid of data points, denoted \underline{x}_i . Let the measurements be written as follow:

$$\tilde{\underline{u}}(x_i) = \underline{u}_{ex}(x_i) + \delta \underline{u}(x_i) \quad , \forall i \in [1, N] \quad (1)$$

where $\delta \underline{u}$ represents the perturbation on the measurements and \underline{u}_{ex} is the exact mechanical field. The aim of the reconstruction is to yield a strain field as close as possible to the one associated with \underline{u}_{ex} .

The reconstruction operator being linear (see 2.2), one can split the reconstruction of $\tilde{\underline{u}}$ as the sum of the reconstruction of the exact field \underline{u}_{ex} and the one of the perturbation alone. The reconstructed field $\underline{u}_{ap}(\underline{x})$, at any \underline{x} , can therefore be written as:

$$\underline{u}_{ap}(\underline{x}) = \underline{u}_{ex}(\underline{x}) + \delta \underline{u}_k(\underline{x}) + \delta \underline{u}_b(\underline{x}) \quad (2)$$

where $\delta \underline{u}_k(\underline{x})$ is the approximation error due to the filtering of the exact field and $\delta \underline{u}_b(\underline{x})$ is the error due to the noise. The same splitting can be applied to the reconstructed strain field ϵ_{ap} .

2.2 The Diffuse Approximation (DA) as a filtering tool

The proposed approach is based on the use of local weighted least-squares [6]. Here, the local regression tool is the Diffuse Approximation [1]. The parameter controlling the filtering is the the span of the influence zone of each data point. One keypoint of the method is that it yields both a continuous displacement field and its derivatives (in a diffuse way) at ones, as explained in the following.

The reconstructed field is sought at any point of Ω , as the solution of the following minimization problem:

$$\min_{a(\underline{x})} \frac{1}{2} \left(P\{a\} - \tilde{U} \right)^T W \left(P\{a\} - \tilde{U} \right) \quad \text{with, } P = \begin{bmatrix} p(\underline{x} - \underline{x}_1) \\ \dots \\ p(\underline{x} - \underline{x}_N) \end{bmatrix}_{i \in V(\underline{x})} \quad (3)$$

where $p(x)$ is the line vector of the monomials of the approximation basis, which is not to be necessarily polynomial. Here, polynomial basis of degree 2 is chosen, because, it appeared in [5] it was a good compromise between filtering and approximation error. With such a basis, the terms $a_2(\underline{x})$ and $a_3(\underline{x})$ represent the first order derivatives at point \underline{x} in a diffuse way. $V(\underline{x})$ represents the neighbourhood of x collecting the data points \underline{x}_i taken into account in the reconstruction at point \underline{x} . The matrix W is a diagonal matrix made of the weighting functions $w(\underline{x}, \underline{x}_i)$ which ensure the continuity of the solution. The weighting functions are such that they equal zero outside the neighbourhood $V(\underline{x})$, whose size is described by the span R .

2.3 Theoretical filtering of the noise

The minimization problem of quadratic criterium (3) leads to the solving of a linear system. This means, as suggested above, that one can study individually the filtering of the noise and the approximation error related to the use of too large influence span R .

Denoting M_ε the strain reconstruction operator and assessing the perturbation are a white gaussian noise sample with known standard deviation γ , the covariance matrix of the reconstructed strain can be characterized as follow:

$$COV(\delta\varepsilon_b) = \gamma^2 M_\varepsilon M_\varepsilon^T \quad (4)$$

Figure 1 presents the ratio of the standard deviation of ε_{XX} and the standard deviation of the

Figure 1: Standard deviation on ε_{XX} as a function of the span R and the offset, logscale

measurements noise as a function of the span R and the offset of the reconstruction point with respect to its neighbourhood $V(\underline{x})$ (a non-zero offset would occur when reconstructing the strain close to an edge of the data area). The increase of the span R improves the filtering and the offset implies a larger span R in order to keep the same filtering quality.

3 Tuning of the span R from experimental results

3.1 Experiment and measurements

The following examples are based on a traction test on an interlock composite. During the test images are taken with a digital camera and then treated by Digital Image Correlation (DIC), by the software CorreliQ4 [2] in order to obtain the displacement fields on the measurement zone. The software CorreliQ4 is based on a Finite Element formulation of the optical correlation problem and its controlling is mainly based, for the end-user, on the meshsize, denoted as the variable ZOI (standing for Zone Of Interest, as in the previous versions of the correlation tool). As for the span R for the Diffuse Approximation, the increase of the ZOI would enhance the filtering of the noise but would increase the approximation error due to the filtering of the mechanical field. These two effects are coupled but their evolution with the ZOI does not behave the same way as their evolution with the span R in the Diffuse Approximation step. Therefore a question to address is to a good value for the couple (ZOI, R) in order to get results as good as possible.

In order to address this question, two criteria will be studied, firstly the whole heterogeneous strain field reconstructed on the measurement zone and, then, the mean strain and its standard deviation under a virtual gauge centered on the zone.

3.2 Filtering of the experimental noise

Figure 2: Standard deviation of ϵ_{XX} as a function of the span R

During the tests, the measurement perturbations on the displacements are not exactly white noise samples. Even if the method is not currently able to filter the deterministic part of the perturbation (which would imply some mechanical considerations), we aim at verifying that our white noise hypothesis is reasonable and that the filtering on real measurements is as expected from a theoretical point of view. To that purpose, the DA filtering is applied on displacements coming from CorreliQ4 applied on two images, both taken before the loading of the specimen. There are hence no displacement and the signal can be considered as a typical perturbation. Figure 2(a) shows the standard deviation under a virtual strain gauge as a function of the span R of the Diffuse Approximation (R is given in *pixels* of the original digital image). The standard deviation is drawn for three ZOI and in the theoretical case of a white gaussian noise, the magnitude being scaled to the experimental one. One can note that the curves for the three ZOI are in the continuity of each other, yielding a global curve very analogous to the theoretical one. For a given span R , the increase of the ZOI increases the filtering of the noise. This could explain the discrepancy between the theoretical and experimental curves, the latter being the result of two filterings (one through CorreliQ4 and one through the DA filtering). Nonetheless, the model of the noise seems

appropriate and this study, before loading, allowed us to characterize the magnitude of the error due to the noise $\delta\epsilon_b$.

3.3 Experimental strain field - effect of ZOI and R

In this section, the strain fields reconstructed for various span R and ZOI are compared for a given load during the traction test. The strain field presented on Figure 3 is the ϵ_{XX} field. The subfigures with a ZOI of 8 pixels show the effect of the span R on the filtering and the approximation. It seems that an intermediate span R leads to a good compromise. The use of a larger ZOI (in particular $ZOI = 32$ pixels) seems to yield a larger approximation error without significant improvement of the filtering. In this example, a ZOI of 8 pixels and a radius between 32 and 48 pixels seem appropriate.

Figure 3: Strain field ϵ_{XX} reconstructed for various couples (ZOI, R)

3.4 A pragmatic criterium for the choice of the span R and the ZOI

A first criterium is proposed in order to help choosing the value of the couple of parameters (ZOI, R) . The standard deviation of the strain under the virtual gauge is due to two distinct reasons: the unfiltered perturbations and the spatial variation of the heterogeneous mechanical strain field. In section 3.2, the evolution of the error due to the noise as a function of the span R of the Diffuse Approximation has been studied and its experimental magnitude characterized. One can therefore superimpose the theoretical curve of the standard deviation as a function of R (scaled to the level of noise of the experiment) to the one of the standard deviation under the virtual gauge for a given load, as in Figure 2(b). When the standard deviation under the virtual gauge reaches a level lower than the minimum level corresponding to the filtering of the noise (horizontal line on Figure 2(b)), one can assure that the filtering is affecting the quality of the mechanical field. Therefore, around the horizontal line, there is a compromise to be found between filtering and loss of the deterministic information. On our example, a ZOI of 32 pixels is too large and the compromise

of a *ZOI* of 8 *pixels* and a span R of 32 *pixels* proposed in section 3.2 is confirmed by this simple criterium.

4 Detection of non-linearities during the test

In this last section, the ϵ_{XX} strain field is studied along a traction test in order to detect the development of local-nonlinearities. The following example is based on a $\pm 45^\circ$ traction test on an interlock carbon composite with several loadings and unloadings as described in Figure 4. Digital Image Correlation (DIC) is performed on about 500 images coming from the test, a large number of pictures is thus available. The DIC is performed with CorreliQ4, with a *ZOI* of 8 *pixels*. From

Figure 4: Loading as a function of the time - the six studied parts

the ideas proposed in [3], one can define the linear approximation of the strain at each pixel on several parts of the test. As represented on Figure 4, six different parts of the test are chosen for this study, each made up of about 20 snapshots. For each part, the linear response is estimated from the corresponding N_k snapshots, $i \in \{1, \dots, N_k\}$, F_i being the corresponding load, as the slope of the response of each pixel:

$$\min_{\epsilon_{lin}^k} \sum_i^{N_k} \left(F_i \epsilon_{lin}^k - \epsilon(x, F_i) \right)^2 \quad \text{with, for the } k^{th} \text{ part} \quad (5)$$

ϵ_{lin}^k represents the linear approximation field for a load of 1 N .

Figure 5: Linear approximation of the strain field ϵ_{XX} for the various parts

These fields are represented on Figure 5 for a span R of 64 *pixels* for the different studied parts of the test. Considering Figure 5(a), the mean of the linear approximation on the first three parts

is plotted, and will be considered as the elastic strain field ϵ_{lin}^{ref} of the specimen, before damage occurs. The other maps are referred by their chronological numbers from Figure 4.

From these fields, it is possible to define a gap to the elastic strain for each part as the discrepancy between the linear approximation related to the part and the reference elastic strain field.

$$\Delta\epsilon_{lin}^{k,ref}(\underline{x}) = \epsilon_{lin}^k(\underline{x}) - \epsilon_{lin}^{ref}(\underline{x}) \quad (6)$$

These $\Delta\epsilon_{lin}^{k,ref}$ fields are drawn on Figure 6 for a span R of 64 pixels. Figure 6(a) gives an idea of the effect of the noise, since it compares the third part with the reference, and there should be very little mechanical discrepancy. Its magnitude is lower than on the following maps. One can note that the strain increases (due to local damage) on the upper part of the zone in a first time, inducing an unloading of the central zone. In a second time, it seems, the damage propagates to the whole zone following alternative $\pm 45^\circ$ strips damaging and unloading. This tendency is confirmed by

Figure 6: Discrepancy to the elastic strain: $\Delta\epsilon_{lin}^{k,ref}$ (6)

the Figure 7 where the incremental discrepancy is plotted. This discrepancy is defined as:

$$\Delta\epsilon_{lin}^{k+1,k}(\underline{x}) = \epsilon_{lin}^{k+1}(\underline{x}) - \epsilon_{lin}^k(\underline{x}) \quad (7)$$

Figure 7: Incremental discrepancy field: $\Delta\epsilon_{lin}^{k+1,k}$ (7)

Finally, Figure 8 presents the effect of the span R on the discrepancy field $\Delta\epsilon_{lin}^{5,ref}$ between the strain coming from part 5 and the reference. On this example, it is obvious that a span R of 64 pixels is too large and some local information is lost. Thanks to the large number of snapshots (about 60) used for the estimate of ϵ_{lin}^{ref} , a good filtering of the noise is achieved and one can afford to take a smaller span R to get more detailed local nonlinearities. Nonetheless, Figure 9 shows the same reconstruction with same the color range from the linear strain coming from part 3 alone. It can be seen that small spans leads to strains dominated by the noise. A span R of 64 pixels, if too large, allows at least to find out where the main zones of damage appears, in such

an example. This last example suggests that by taking more snapshots one can afford to reduce the span R and therefore reduce the approximation error. To that purpose, an evolution of the Diffuse Approximation filtering tool has been developed in order to filter the displacement both in time and space [7].

Figure 8: Discrepancy between part 5 and the reference: $\Delta\epsilon_{lin}^{5,ref}$ - effect of the span R

Figure 9: Discrepancy between part 5 and part 3: $\Delta\epsilon_{lin}^{5,3}$ - effect of the span R

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we presented an approach based on the Diffuse Approximation to reconstruct the strain fields from measured displacement fields. The keypoint of such a tool is to control the error due to the noise on the displacement. The parameter that controls the errors (in terms of both approximation and noise) is the span R of the Diffuse Approximation and has to be chosen in order to yield a good balance between the two types of error. The approach has been applied to experimental tests on interlock composites and appeared to be relevant in such a case with large heterogeneities. A first pragmatic criterium has been proposed in order to help the user for the choice of the parameters of both the correlation tool and the Diffuse Approximation. By combining th filtering to the estimate of the linear approximation of the strain on various parts of the test, the development of local non-linearities could be detected. The use of too large span R yields too much loss of local mechanical information but remains relevant in order to help understanding the qualitative behaviour of the specimen during the test. To use smaller values of the span R , it was shown that one has to evaluate the linear approximations on more snapshots and this confirms the interest of one of the current developments of the method, which is the application of space-time diffuse approximation to the filtering of displacement full-field measurements.

References

- [1] B. Nayroles, G. Touzot, P. Villon. La méthode des éléments diffus. *Comptes rendus de l'Académie des Sciences, série 2, Mécanique, Physique, Chimie, Sciences de l'Univers, Sciences de la Terre*, 313-2, 133–138, 1991.
- [2] G. Besnard, F. Hild, S. Roux. Finite-element displacement fields analysis from digital images: Application to Portevin-Le Châtelier bands. *Experimental Techniques*, 46, 789–803, 2006.
- [3] F Pierron, B. Green and M R Wisnom. Full-field assessment of the damage process of laminated composite open-hole tensile specimens. Part II: Experimental results
Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 38-11,2321–2332 2007.
- [4] F. J. Hickernell and Y. C. Hon. Radial basis function approximations as smoothing splines. *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, 102–1,1–24 1999.
- [5] S. Avril, P. Feissel, F. Pierron, P. Villon. Estimation of strain field from full-field displacement noisy data. *Revue Européenne de Mécanique Numérique*, Lavoisier, 17.5–7,857–868 2008.
- [6] W.S. Cleveland, C. Loader *Smoothing by local regression: principles and methods*, Springer, 1995.
- [7] T. Roland, P. Feissel, M. Risbet, D. Brancherie and J.M. Roelandt Étude de l’amorçage d’un acier par corrélation d’images *Congrès Français de Mécanique*, Marseille, France, August 2009, submitted